

COMPARATIVE-SEMANTICAL ANALYSIS OF THE LEXEMES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK PROVERBS

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Abstract:

Language is the mirror of the nation. It is impossible to imagine the language without literary devices, literary elements, figurative language and folklore, and they make speech beautiful, attractive and impressive to the listeners. One of such elements is proverb. Sayings help to express idea as a short advice. But they can be used as connotative phrase. As Bahodir Sarimsoqov said: "Proverbs can be used as both figuratively and denotationally. This feature expands the thematic and usage sphere of the proverbs" [3;5]. In this article, lexical features of some proverbs in Uzbek and English language, lexical differences between them, historical forms and meanings of some words in sayings and relevant conclusions on them are addressed.

Key words: figurative language, folklore, saying, lexical feature, moral background, zwaan, Schwan, historical origin.

doi: <https://doi.org/10.2024/ama4an25>

Language can be viewed as the way of communicating and expressing ideas, feelings and emotions with each other for humanity. The proverb plays a great role in the language and daily life of the world nations and it is used as a means of explaining something in a literally, figurative, kind and smart way. Proverbs are also called sayings. The life experience and historical, social, cultural, moral background of the nations can be seen in the proverbs. People use them as a constant tool of the language. Proverbs give some form of life advice. Every language and culture has them, and many proverbs exist in more than one language. It is important not to miss any of the words in most proverbs because the meaning can be lost if even one word is changed or left out. Therefore, it is impossible to change the position of the one word, even, in the proverbs. The proverbs are the conclusions of the life experiences and observations, so nations pay a great deal of attention to the diversity and variety of the words in them. But the sphere of the meaning can be broad or narrow according to their usage. Therefore, language speakers should pay attention to every single word in the sayings.

An English proverb is a brief, to-the-point statement that typically conveys a life experience, a truth, or advice for living. Because proverbs are used so widely, fluent English speakers may unintentionally utilize them in speech. Proverbs are frequently used as examples to make a point. Because they are more metaphorical or symbolic in character, they differ stylistically from conventional forms of speech. While most proverbs are universally accepted and

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frequently passed down through the years, others may be representative of a particular culture or location. Additionally, proverbs can provide a quick explanation or method of conveying knowledge. For example, rather than the manager in one company saying, “We will only be successful if we approach the client before any other marketing firm reaches out to them,” she can simplify this explanation to “the early bird catches the worm.” Everyone in the meeting will know what she means. Proverbs communicate an understood and accepted message in a few well-worn and well-known words [6].

In fact, some of the earliest recorded proverbs date back to the ancient Sumerians in 2000 BCE. According to archaeological studies, nearly 700 tablets containing more than 1,000 proverbs written by Sumerian scribes were discovered by researchers. When translated, the researchers were surprised at how easy it was to understand these snippets of Sumerian wisdom, showing how proverbs reach across cultures and time [5]. English proverbs should also not be mistaken for the Book of Proverbs, a book in the Old Testament.

There are such kind of words which have other meaning historically, but mean another one in present day. For example, “Every man thinks his own geese swans” [7]. Here, the word “swan” is from the Old English, of Germanic origin; related to Dutch *zwaan* and German *Schwan*. The current sense of the word originated as military slang, referring to the free movement of armoured vehicles. But now it means “a large bird that is usually white and has along thin neck. Swans live on or near water [8].

Such kind of examples can be seen in Uzbek language, too. For instance, the word “tuz” (salt) means “mineral substance” nowadays, but it meant “correct, right, tactful or field, plane” historically. It is kept in sayings as the form “Qiz saqlasang, tuz saqla” or “Tuzdagi bilan emas, uydagi bilan boʻl” [1;57]. Also, in the belowmentioned saying the word “mehnat” means “torment, misery” in some proverbs or dialects: “Davlat ham egiz, mehnat ham egiz” [2;25].

In addition to this, there are some proverbs which cannot be translated from English into Uzbek directly. For instance, the proverb “first impressions are the most lasting” means that “I should attempt to show my personality, by my neat clothes, good communication and professional skills for the first time when I meet the manager. Otherwise, the manager will hardly change his attitude towards me or seems to be strange no matter I will try to behave myself positively next time”. We translated the proverb “First impressions are the most lasting” word-for-word as “Birinchi taassurot juda uzoq davom etadi”. We considered some information is missing in translation, for this reason in our translation, we added some Uzbek phrases like “kishi xotirasida”.

Or in this example “Fingers were made before forks”- “Men qoʻlimda yeyman, men qoʻlimda yeyaveraman/yoki oʻzimni qoʻlimdan qoʻymasin”. This proverb expresses that someone who prefers eating with their fingers instead of utensils [9]. We can see a cultural key word, “forks” which shows British people are accustomed to eating most foods with a fork, a knife, and spoon. A word-for-word Uzbek translation of this proverb is “Barmoqlar sanchqilardan avval paydo boʻlgan”. Although the word “sanchqilar” is associated with food, whole sentence can hardly provide the meaning of the original proverb. Moreover, there is no equivalent to this proverb so we omitted the word “forks” and translated the proverb freely by considering the whole.

Besides, the proverb “Don’t put all your eggs in one basket” – “Boringni biringga tikma” can also be a good example to the abovementioned point. It can be seen that this phrase is simply proverbial sentence, but it is actually an

idiomatic expression. It implies that eggs are easily broken or damaged object. Typically, we may buy eggs and put them into a particular container, for example, a basket. Suddenly because of a big dog, we dropped the basket and all of those eggs were damaged. Certainly, it is not a tragedy losing a basket of eggs; in reality, this proverb advises not to repeat this action in a serious activity, like spending all money in an unsuccessful business which leads to bankruptcy. There is an Uzbek equivalent “Suvni koʻrmay, etik yechma” (Don’t put off your boots without seeing water) as Makhmud Koshgari (IX century) defined that it is a warning that everyone should consider something carefully before making a decision, otherwise its result may harm them[4;56]. Although don’t put all your eggs in one basket and don’t put off your boots without seeing water lexically different they share a similar meaning. Suvni koʻrmay, etik yechma is a conceptual equivalent, so we presented the Uzbek translation as “Boringni biringga tikma” by studying the meaning of the proverb “Don’t put all your eggs in one basket”.

To conclude, in most cases proverbs are used to illustrate a point. Stylistically, they differ from regular forms of speech because they are metaphorical or symbolic in nature. Some proverbs can be reflective of a specific culture or locale, though the majority transcend regional barriers and are widely embraced and often passed down through generations.

As it is seen, some words in proverbs have different meaning now, but different meaning in the past. Or some words can be used in their connotative and denotative meanings. Proverbs have a literal meaning and tend to express a truth or dispense advice such as actions speak louder than words; all’s well that ends well; a leopard never changes its spots. The stylistic devices such as anaphor, metaphor, alliteration, irony are used in proverbs. These features can help to understand light humour, true confirmation and deep meaning which is hidden in the sayings. The features like the short form, meaningful content, live theme of the proverbs have been helping to pass down through generations and they are the main factors in order to live the sayings till now.

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